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THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MUSCLE CONTRACTURES AND THE USE OF CORTICOSTEROIDS IN CHILDREN WITH DUCHENNE MUSCULAR DYSTROPHY

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Introduction. Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD) is associated with an increased risk of muscle contractures. Corticosteroids are used as a form of drug therapy in the treatment of children with DMD. The aim of the study was to determine whether there is a connection between muscle contractures and the use of corticosteroids.

Participants and methods. The study included 19 male patients, aged between 10-16 years with different functional ability. 31.6% of participants had the first level on the functionality scale, 5.3% were on the fourth level, while the highest percentage had the V level of the AFCSD scale (63.2%).

Results. The average age of the boys was 14 years, 83.3 % of patients had contractures. The most common localization of contractures is in the lower extremities, where the first place in frequency are contractures in the knee joint and ankle joint, with a representation of 73.68% each. In our study, 41.2 % of patients use corticosteroid therapy.

Conclusion. There is no significant statistical difference in the occurrence of contractures in the group of patients who are on corticosteroid therapy and the group of patients who do not use this type of therapy. As a form of prevention of the occurrence of contractures on the lower extremities, regular application of stretching exercises should be started immediately after the established diagnosis of DMD.